

A Comprehensive review on Biochar: Its Production and effect on soil properties

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Abstract:

Biochar, a byproduct of biomass combustion, is a form of carbon that is extremely concentrated. Biochar, a byproduct of biodegradable material, is gaining attention as a potential solution to numerous urgent ecological issues. Biochar contributes to the battle against global warming due to its efficiency in carbon sequestration. Biochar, when applied to soil, may increase soil fertility and agricultural output. Biochar, also known as "biomass derived black carbon" or charcoal, has the potential to function as a reservoir for carbon. Erosion and the loss of nitrogen through discharge are two main factors contributing to deteriorating soil health. Biochar has been demonstrated to increase crop yields, increase soil fertility, and decrease pollution. This article discusses biochar, including its production methods, nutrient content, characteristics, applications in soil, and capacity to detoxify soil of heavy metals.

Keywords: Biochar, Leaching, Depletion, Biomass, Remediation

Introduction:

Char is a solid refuse by-product of the combustion of carbonaceous materials (Amin et al., 2016). Charcoal, for instance, is reportedly one of the oldest products ever produced by humans using fire or heat. Frequently, charcoal-based products have a high carbon content. Biochar is another frequent instance of char. Unlike charcoal, the substance at issue in this case is composed solely of organic materials such as wood, vegetation, and animals. Biochar is produced when fuel burns at temperatures below 700 °C in the absence of a significant amount of oxygen (Armah et al., 2021). The first application of biochar was in soil, where it was used for a variety of purposes, such as carbon storage, enhancing soil water permeability, nutrient availability, soil compaction, and increasing pH. Current applications include energy production, ecological maintenance, and environmental mitigation (Amin FR et al., 2016; Borel et al., 2018; Borel et al., 2020). Carbonized biological matter has characteristics that are defined by its source or input material and by the production factors that are essential for its creation. Slow or rapid pyrolysis and gasification are the two most prevalent techniques for producing biochar. The chemical composition of the input biomass has a direct effect on the physical properties of the biochar. At temperatures exceeding 120 °C, the preponderance of organic components degrades due to heat. Hemicelluloses decompose at temperatures between 200 and 260 degrees Celsius; cellulose decomposes between 240 and 350 degrees Celsius; and lignin decomposes between 280 and 500 degrees Celsius (Lee et al., 2019). In turn, the reactivity of these elements and, consequently, the degree to which their physical properties are altered as a result of processing are dependent on their relative abundances (Zhou et al., 2021). The carbon content of biochar derived from plants is between 51 and 92.4%. For current and prospective biochar applications, a greater comprehension of the mechanisms that significantly alter the physiochemical characteristics of the feedstock is crucial.

To enhance the current and future applications of biochar, it will be necessary to analyze the processes that contribute to significant changes in biochar's physio-chemical properties,

which will require a comprehensive comprehension of a wide range of feedstock types and processing techniques. This review concentrates on the methods currently used to create biochar, the factors that determine its composition and characteristics, and its potential use in agriculture.

Biochar as Nutrient Source:

The total nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium content of biochar may not be directly proportional to the amount of these nutrients that are available to plants as ammonium, nitrate, phosphate, and potassium ions (Spokas et al., 2012), but it may be related to this. Due to nitrogen depletion in biochar, there is less nitrogen available at higher temperatures (Koutcheiko et al., 2007). When the total amount of K increased, so did the amount of usable K (Zheng et al., 2013). Wu et al. (2011) used biochar made from mallee wood to demonstrate that approximately 15–20% Ca and 10–60% P are readily leachable with distilled water, with the precise percentages varying with temperature and the plant region studied. Nevertheless, this method of determining the total levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in biochar can be used as a de facto method for selecting the finest biochar in a practical application (Wu et al., 2011).

Methods of Biochar Production:

Biochar is being produced from an expanding amount of biomass to satisfy the growing demand for its many applications. Conventionally, biochar is produced through thermochemical conversion. Thermochemical conversion processes include torrefaction, gasification, hydrothermal carbonization, and pyrolysis (Pang, 2019; Lin et al., 2016).

Pyrolysis:

Pyrolysis, according to Osayi et al. (2014), refers to the breakdown of biomass compounds under specific temperatures (ranging from 250 to 900 °C) in the absence of oxygen. Without a strong oxidizing agent, biomass cannot undergo thermochemical degradation, making gasification impractical (Nyazika et al., 2019). Agricultural residue primarily comprises silica, lignin, cellulose, and hemicelluloses. For lignin to dissolve and cellulose to undergo pyrolysis, temperatures exceeding 350 degrees Celsius are required. Czernik and Bridgwater's Pyrolysis technique, as observed, is most effective within the temperature range of 300 to 700 °C (Suarez-Abelenda et al., 2017). Despite being an anaerobic process, pyrolysis necessitates various heat sources, including oxidation and partial oxidation processes, hot gases, heated substances, a liquid heat transfer medium, and the pyrolysis itself (Li et al., 2016; Xie et al., 2015). Manufacturing temperature significantly influences product quality, with higher pyrolysis temperatures resulting in decreased biochar production and increased syngas production. Pyrolysis can occur at different rates, either slowly or rapidly (Wei et al., 2019).

Fig. 1: Mechanism of Pyrolysis

with the help of modern technology new methods were adopted with better efficiency which include, microwave, vacuum, and flash pyrolysis. The mechanism of pyrolysis is shown below.

Table 1: Biochar production using Conventional and Modern methods

S.no	Biochar production method	Condition	Application	Reference
1	Slow pyrolysis	Temperature range: 300-600 °C Heating rate: 5 – 7 °C/min	Syngas and Bio oil are used as energy fuel and soil improvement.	(Lai et al.,2013)
2	Fast pyrolysis	Temperature range: >500 °C Heating rate: 300 C/min	Soil improvement, absorbent, and biogas.	(Huang et al., 2017)
3	Flash pyrolysis	Temperature range : 900 – 1200 oC Heating rate: 800 – 1000 °C/sec	Syngas, bio-oil, and soil improvement.	(Li et al., 2013)
4	Vacuum pyrolysis	Temperature range :450 – 600 oC Heating rate: 300 °C/min Pressure: 0.05 – 0.20 MPa	High porosity, Mineral absorption, and soil improvement.	(Carrier et al.,2014)
5	Microwave pyrolysis	Temperature: 450 – 800 °C Microwave power: 400 – 800 W Microwave frequency: 2450 MHz	Syngas, bio-oil, and soil improvement.	(Huang et al., 2017)

Slow Pyrolysis

Slow pyrolysis is a time-consuming process that yields a substantial amount of biochar. Slow pyrolysis, also known as conventional pyrolysis, is the process of heating biomass between 300 and 600 °C at a rate of 5 to 7 °C min⁻¹ (Lai et al., 2013). Slow pyrolysis can generate biochar (35–45%), bio-oil (25–35%), syngas (20–30%), and additional residues (Lai et al., 2013; Mendez et al., 2015; Verma et al., 2012). As suggested by Verma et al. (2012), in the slow pyrolysis process, a continuous auger or screw pyrolyzer reactor is often employed, ensuring a methodical and regulated transformation of biomass into biochar. Slow pyrolysis, where wood particles are heated between 290 and 700 degrees Celsius at a rate of approximately 30 degrees Celsius per minute for two hours, produces biochar (Lai et al., 2013). Biochar was produced from deinking wastewater using a gradual pyrolysis process in a confined steel cup heated at 10 C/min (Mendez et al., 2015). Biochar was generated in a Daisy Reactor at Best Energies via a gradual pyrolysis process, employing a heterogeneous mix of feedstocks, including sawdust, bovine manure, pinewood, oak wood, dairy manure amalgamated with rice hulls, hazelnut shells, maize, culinary refuse, and effluent from white paper mills. (McBeath et al., 2014). It has been demonstrated that, for biochar synthesis, a delayed pyrolysis rate is preferable to a quicker one (Moralí and Sensoz, 2015).

Fast Pyrolysis

Fast pyrolysis represents a viable thermochemical pathway for the production of hydrocarbons from biomass. (Dai et al., 2017). Fast pyrolysis has the benefits of decreased retention time and increased product recovery. When the technology is improved to produce fuels or fuel mixtures, syngas and bio-oil, not charcoal, are the primary outputs (Huang et al., 2016). Rapid pyrolysis is conducted in an anaerobic environment at temperatures exceeding 500 °C over a thermal range exceeding 300 °C/min. Fast pyrolysis is a time-saving process that generates biochar in seconds. Fast pyrolysis yields sixty percent bio-oil, twenty percent charcoal, and twenty percent syngas (Dai et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2016). It is possible to remove salicylic acid, 4-nitroaniline, phthalic acid, and benzoic acid from water using biochar derived from rapid pyrolysis due to its superior adsorption properties (Karunanayake et al., 2017). According to Laird et al. (2017), the advantages of biochar on crop yields and soil quality are greatest when it is produced from hard timber via rapid pyrolysis.

Flash Pyrolysis

The technique of pyrolysis is a refined variant of rapid pyrolysis. This process is also known as ultra-fast pyrolysis (Amutio et al., 2012) due to its rapid heating and temperature, brief vapor residence time (i.e., 1 s), rapid cooling of vapor, and eradication of carbon at the conclusion of pyrolysis. At or above 1000 °C, biomass decomposes rapidly, typically in less than a minute. For flash pyrolysis, temperatures of 900–1,200 °C must be reached in less than one second (Demirbas and Arin, 2002; Ghodake et al., 2012). Tripathi et al. (2015) and Tripathi et al. (2022) discovered that increasing the heating rate, the temperature, and the vapor residence time all led to an increase in bio-oil production. Several factors, such as biomass phase transition behavior, response chemical kinetics, heat and mass transport processes, and reaction kinetics, influence the distribution of the final products in flash pyrolysis. Since flash pyrolysis requires a high operating temperature and a rapid heating rate, reactor designs such as the fluidized bed reactor and the twin-screw mixing reactor have limited industrial applications (Gabhane et al., 2020).

Vacuum Pyrolysis

Vacuum pyrolysis is the process of utilizing heat to decompose biomass in an oxygen-depleted or pressurized environment (Tripathi et al., 2016; Lam et al., 2019). The standard pressure range is between 0.5 and 2 bar (Carrier et al., 2011), while the temperature range is between 450 and 600 degrees Celsius. Compared to sluggish pyrolysis, the rate of combustion decreases. Vapors produced by vacuum pyrolysis are continuously and effectively released by the condensation process, resulting in a variety of distinct effects. This procedure produces char and hydrocarbon byproducts at a lower decomposition temperature (Liu et al., 2018; De Jongh et al., 2011). As a consequence of the swift removal of organic vapours in the initial pyrolysis stage, the duration of vapor residence is significantly curtailed, thereby diminishing the probability of subsequent reactions and guaranteeing an elevated yield of liquid products in the subsequent pyrolysis phase. (Chen et al., 2018). Using vacuum or low-pressure extraction alone prevents inorganic disintegration, which has a significant impact on both product quality and yield.

Decomposition of Carbohydrates

During the pyrolysis process, biochar is created from a variety of materials, most of which include carbohydrates like cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, each of which reacts uniquely depending on the operating circumstances. Because of this, biochar production during pyrolysis might be affected (Tripathi et al., 2016). Specifically, lignin and cellulose make up the vast majority of biomass (Chen et al., 2018). Pyrolysis of lignin yields char and a small quantity of water, whereas cellulose yields tar, a combination of ketones, aldehydes, organic liquids, and char (Yu et al., 2014). When there is a concomitant increase in cellulose content and a reduction in char and tar content, more gas is produced. It has also been discovered that structural differences in the biomass alter the pyrolysis product's composition (Yu et al., 2014).

Decomposition of cellulose:

When the degree of polymerization is reduced, the two-stage process of cellulose degradation is identified. In gradual pyrolysis, cellulose is broken down at a low temperature over an extended period of time. At high temperatures, levoglucosan is produced by rapid pyrolysis and rapid evaporation. Levoglucosan can be converted into bio-oil, syngas, and biochar (a solid byproduct) by removing the water. Moreover, aromatization, condensation, and polymerization are viable methods for converting hydroxymethylfurfural to solid biochar (Edward et al., 2022; Lindstrom et al., 2019). Large quantities of char are produced by the low-temperature degradation of cellulose to the exceptionally stable hydrocellulose molecule, which emits volatile compounds (Reza et al., 2019).

Decomposition of Hemicellulose:

Hemicellulose is decomposed in the same manner as cellulose. The depolymerization of hemicellulose results in the formation of oligosaccharides (Yang et al., 2019). Using decarboxylation, intramolecular rearrangement, depolymerization, and aromatization, biochar can be converted into syngas and bio-oil (Huang et al., 2012).

Decomposition of Lignin:

Lignin degradation is more difficult than cellulose and hemicellulose degradation because lignin is composed of a simple sugar monomer that decomposes above 450 °C (Lee et al., 2013; Mu et al., 2013). In contrast to cellulose and hemicellulose, however, lignin is more resistant to thermal decomposition due to its higher molecular weight (Tomczyk et al., 2020). Sohi et al. (2010) and Wang et al. (2014) found a relationship between increases in biochar carbon and ash content and plant biomass with a higher lignin concentration. By dissolving relatively weak connections, lignin-derived char is formed with a more compact solid structure (Santos et al., 2013). When the O-4 lignin bond is broken, free radicals are liberated. When free radicals absorb protons from other particles, they degrade other substances. When free radicals migrate to other molecules, chains may form. Due to differences in lignin composition, various varieties of wood degrade at different rates. Compared to deciduous trees, conifers have a more stable lignin content, which may account for their higher char content (Brebou et al., 2010; Ma et al., 2022).

Hydrothermal Carbonization:

Hydrothermal carbonization is preferred to other biochar production techniques because it can be carried out at moderate temperatures (180–250 °C; Lee et al., 2018). Hydrothermal char is the name given to the byproduct of the hydrothermal process to differentiate it from byproducts of dry processes such as pyrolysis and gasification (Fang et al., 2018). The biomass is combined with water and then placed in a reactor that has been hermetically sealed. Gradually increasing the temperature until equilibrium is attained. The hydrothermal carbonization process, which produces biochar at temperatures below 250 °C (Zhang et al., 2018), produces the following byproducts: Bio-oil is extracted by hydrothermal liquefaction at temperatures ranging from 250 to 400 degrees Celsius ("average") and pressures between 10 and 25 megapascals (MPa). Hydrothermal gasification at temperatures greater than 400 degrees Celsius generates syngas composed of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, hydrogen, and methane (Khorram et al., 2016). The synthesis of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural and its derivatives as intermediate products from the hydrolyzed product can occur via a variety of processes, such as dehydration, fragmentation, and isomerization. Furthermore, intramolecular dehydration, condensation, and polymerization all contribute to the formation of hydrochar (Bakraoui et al., 2020). It is difficult to comprehend the mechanism of lignin because of its high molecular mass and compact structure. Dealkylation and hydrolysis result in the formation of phenolic compounds such as phenols, catechols, and syringols during the degradation of lignin (Jain et al., 2016). Repolymerization and cross-linking of intermediates culminate in the formation of char. Hydrochar is produced by the same transformation that takes place during pyrolysis with insoluble lignin components. Depending on the temperature conditions, hydrothermal carbonization generates a variety of byproducts, such as biochar, bio-oil, and syngas.

Fig 2: Hydrothermal Carbonization

Gasification:

Syngas is a resultant output of a thermochemical procedure transforming carbon-rich substances into a gaseous blend comprising carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), hydrogen (H₂), and minute traces of hydrocarbons. (Dasappa and Shivapuji, 2022; Galindo et al., 2014). Gasification occurs at temperatures between 700 and 900 °C in the absence or presence of significant amounts of oxidizing agents such as carbon dioxide, nitrogen, oxygen, steam, or a combination of these gases. Carbon monoxide and hydrogen are produced at a higher rate at higher temperatures, while methane, carbon dioxide, and hydrocarbons are produced at a lower rate (Prabakar et al., 2018). The byproducts (waste) of gasification include syngas, char, charcoal, and creosote, as well as compounds containing hydrogen. Carbon in biomass is converted into combustible combustion gases, which can be utilized more effectively and conveniently than unprocessed biomass (Maitlo et al., 2022). The relationship between pyrolysis and gasification is close. Gasification and pyrolysis produce identical outcomes when combined (Ruiz et al., 2013; Bisht and Thakur, 2020). The gasification procedure alters the characteristics of the final product by subjecting the biomass to partial oxidation. An important distinction between pyrolysis and gasification is the product's composition. Gasification is estimated by Tripathi et al. (2016), Bisht and Thakur (2020), and others to produce approximately 85% gases, 10% solid carbon, and 5% liquids. Carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), hydrogen (H₂), and trace quantities of hydrocarbon (H₂) make up syngas, which is a byproduct of the thermochemical conversion of carbon-rich materials (Dasappa and Shivapuji, 2022). 2014, The Galindo

Group Gasification occurs at temperatures between 700 and 900 °C in the absence or presence of significant amounts of oxidizing agents such as carbon dioxide, nitrogen, oxygen, steam, or a combination of these gases. Carbon monoxide and hydrogen are produced at a higher rate at higher temperatures, while methane, carbon dioxide, and hydrocarbons are produced at a lower rate (Prabakar et al., 2018). The byproducts (waste) of gasification include syngas, char, charcoal, and creosote, as well as compounds containing hydrogen. Carbon in biomass is converted into combustible combustion gases, which can be utilized more effectively and conveniently than unprocessed biomass (Maitlo et al., 2022). The relationship between pyrolysis and gasification is close. Gasification and pyrolysis produce identical outcomes when combined (Ruiz et al., 2013; Bisht and Thakur, 2020). The gasification procedure alters the characteristics of the final product by subjecting the biomass to partial oxidation. An important distinction between pyrolysis and gasification is the product's composition.

Fig 3: GASIFICATION PROCESS

Torrefaction:

When biomass is torrefied at temperatures between 230 and 300 degrees Celsius, a higher-quality fuel is produced that can be utilized in combustion and gasification processes (Jagdish et al., 2020). In other words, torrefaction is a pre-treatment process that enhances the physical, chemical, and biological qualities of unprocessed biomass so that it can be utilized more effectively in subsequent processes such as combustion and gasification (Tumuluru et al., 2011; Almeida et al., 2010). Decomposition of the hemicellulose component of wood produces volatiles and torrefied wood, a carbon-rich, more stable solid (Jagdish et al., 2020). In the absence of oxygen, biomass can be treated thermochemically via the torrefaction process. Typically, a fixed-bed reactor is utilized for the torrefaction procedure. (Huang et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2013). research on three distinct forms of agricultural waste: sawdust, coffee grounds, and rice hulls. The rate of hemicellulose degradation in coffee residue was found to be greater than in other biomasses, while the hygroscopicity of all biomasses

increased relative to unprocessed biomass. Chen and Kuo (2010) examined the effects of temperature on the compositional variations of four distinct types of biomass, including wood, bamboo, and coconut shell, during the torrefaction process. According to the study (Chen et al., 2013), cellulose decomposition occurred at high temperatures of acute torrefaction ($>280\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), whereas hemicellulose decomposition occurred at $240\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Factors influencing biochar's characteristics:

1) Feedstock:

Biomass is a composite substance composed of organic, inorganic, and biological components produced by living or nonliving organisms. According to Amin et al. (2016), biomass can be classified as either woody or non-woody. Animal waste, municipal and industrial solid waste, and agricultural crop residue are examples of non-woody biomass (Amin et al., 2016), whereas tree biomass, sawmill scraps, and forest residues are examples of woody biomass. Non-woody biomass has a higher ash and moisture content, a lower bulk density, a lower calorific value, and a greater volume than woody biomass (Edward et al., 2022). Borel et al. (2018) state that the moisture content of the biomass has a significant effect on the physicochemical properties of the produced biochar. According to a study comparing the pyrolytic charcoals derived from hardwood and softwood bark samples (Borel et al., 2020), there is a correlation between the initial sample moisture content and the surface chemistry of the generated charcoal. Scientists discovered that extended pyrolysis periods led to the surface charcoal of maple bark becoming more polyaromatic and graphite-like. Extensive research has been conducted on the effect of feedstock lignin and cellulose levels on biochar synthesis (Edward et al., 2022). In contrast to the simple sugar monomers that make up hemicelluloses and cellulose, which degrade at temperatures below $450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, lignin is an amorphous, hydrophobic, and aromatic polymer with a high molecular weight. As previously demonstrated (Balogun et al., 2017; Azargohar et al., 2019), a greater concentration of lignin in plant biomass facilitates carbonization and increases the carbon and ash contents of biochar.

2) Residence Time:

The biochar yield decreases as the residence time increases. Although it reduced the quantity of biochar that could bind iodine, extending the residence time at the high pyrolysis temperature ($600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) had no impact on pH or biochar production (Liang et al., 2016) which is due to under high temperature if we increase residence time it changes surface of biochar and its internal structure (Braadbaart and Poole 2008).

3) Biomass Pre-Treatment:

Pretreatment of biomass prior to pyrolysis may alter the ultimate characteristics of biochar. Reducing the particle size of biomass and immersing raw materials in solutions are the two most prevalent pre-treatment techniques. When biomass particles are pulverized to a finer consistency, a large quantity of biochar is produced. For example, a moderately acidic solution was used to treat pine wood biomass prior to combustion. Nitrogen and metal enrichment are two pre-treatment strategies that may influence the production and outcome of biochar. Soaking or steaming may modify the elemental composition and properties of biochar, whereas roasting can increase the carbon content and decrease the oxygen and water levels. There are numerous types of biomass that may

be utilized to produce biochar. Depending on the procedure, the moisture or mineral content of the biomass can restrict its practical use. For instance, the presence of chlorine and soluble base metals may result in consumption. Depending on the manufacturing method and feedstock used, the biochar's ultimate characteristics may vary considerably. During pyrolysis, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur are released into the atmosphere, whereas phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, and silica survive and are concentrated in the resulting biochar. The pyrolysis or gasification of polluted biomass could result in the incorporation of hazardous components into biochar (You et al., 2018).

Biochar Applications in Soil:

The addition of biochar can considerably improve soil fertility as fertile soils require a good quantity of aggregates, solids, pore space and organic matter content (or humus), which provides the suitable medium for plant growth and development. Because of its crystalline structure, biochar is extremely stable and durable in soils. Soil with poor physical structure can be improved with biochar application. Application of biochar enhances the degree of porosity and also improve aeration, if soil is too compacted (Heitkotter et al., 2015). The surface area and degree of porosity of biochar are much greater than those of fine, sandy soil types (Dempster et al., 2012). Incorporation of biomass compost in addition to biochar has dual advantage. In the initial stage compost will provide required amount of nutrients to plant due to its faster decomposition rate and then later biochar will also start its gradual release of nutrient Biochar addition to soil revs up internal chemical reactions, benefiting plant growth. Additionally, biochar's long lifespan in soil means it can potentially offer long-term benefits without requiring yearly applications, reducing costs. Biochar addition increases formation of macroaggregates in soil which reduces soil erosion and hence improves water infiltration in the soil (Jien and Wang, 2013). The amounts of soil organic matter decrease with time where weathering, continuous farming and other human activities all contribute to this. When biochar is added to soils, an interesting effect is the increased detection of ethylene, a vital plant hormone used to regulate plant development and ripening (Spokas et al., 2010). The biochar addition will increase crop yields as ethylene production increases (Allohverdi et al., 2021).

Table 2: Effect of biochar on soil chemical properties

S.no	Rate of Biochar (t/ha)	Organic Matter %	pH	CEC (cmol/kg)	References
1	0 t/ha	1.78	5.61	1.1	(Taiwo et al., 2020)
	30 t/ha	2.97	5.96	7.5	
2	0 t/ha	1.62	5.23	2.7	(Nigussie et al., 2011)
	25 t/ha	2.54	5.72	5.9	
3	0 t/ha	1.8	5.13	1.6	(Tao et al., 2019)
	10 t/ha	2.12	5.44	3.48	
4	0 t/ha	1.65	5.6	1.2	(Ayeni et al., 2011)
	30 t/ha	3.18	6.1	8.6	
5	0 t/ha	1.72	5.09	1.9	(Misganaw et al., 2020)
	10 t/ha	2.41	5.42	6.4	

Nutrients and pH

Biochar has the capacity to retain and provide plant-accessible nutrients. Because plants readily assimilate potassium from biochar (Joseph et al., 2010). The degree of availability varies depending on the feedstock and manufacturing conditions (Haque et al., 2021). Biochar application at 0–30 t/ha increases soil organic matter (1.78–2.97%), nitrogen (0.16–0.18%), phosphorus (8.6–14.6 mg/kg), and potassium (0.09–0.14 Cmol/kg) (Adekiya et al., 2020). By enhancing the adsorption of basic cations, the addition of biochar to acidic tropical soils raises the pH, resulting in greater soil fertility (Major et al., 2010). Due to an increase in aromatic carbon oxidation, the CEC of soil rises when biochar is introduced (Liang et al., 2006). Due to the increased CEC, a larger yield is feasible as a consequence of the increased availability of soil nutrients (Rehman and Razzaq, 2017). According to Solaiman and Anwar (2015), biochar can be used to enhance "problem soils," which have issues such as poor aggregate stability, excessive salinity, improper pH levels (either too high or too low), and a deficiency of essential nutrients. Problematic soils contain undesirable biological, physical, or chemical qualities that inhibit plant growth. A single application of biochar may have an enduring impact on the condition of the soil. Diversifying the population of microbes is one strategy for achieving this. Biochar's pores provide sanctuary for microorganisms and aid in the fixation of nitrogen, which plants can then absorb. Biochar increases nitrogen availability for plants, particularly non-legumes that cannot fix their own nitrogen. Zheng et al. (2013) discovered that applying 15 g of biochar per kilogram of soil increased maize yields by 8.2 percentage points. When their physio-chemical properties were analyzed, biochar-treated soils had higher nitrogen levels (1.16% vs. 0.15% soil nitrogen) than soils that had only received fertilizer. (Agegnehu et al., 2017) discovered a correlation between the nitrogen content of plant leaves and a 9–18% rise in biomass. Agricultural residue biochar is frequently more alkaline and contributes to a higher soil pH. A greater quantity of ash in this biochar indicates that more basic ions may be present, thereby increasing the alkalinity of the soil. Kameyama et al. (2012) demonstrated that bagasse biochar is effective at minimizing nitrate leaching in high-calcium soils, which are known to have nutrient retention issues. After pyrolyzing the material at 400–800 degrees Celsius, the CEC was determined. Slow pyrolysis at 600°C yielded two types of biochar, including one with enhanced surface

functionality and a decreased pH. The enhanced surface functionality of biochar, which increases the amount of free carboxylic carbon on the biochar surface, makes cation retention feasible.

Table 3: Effect of biochar on soil nutrient content

S.no	Rate of Biochar (t/ha)	N %	P%	K%	Ca %	References
1	0 t/ha	0.16	8.6	0.09	1.69	(Timothy et al., 2020)
	30 t/ha	0.18	14.6	0.14	2.45	
2	0 t/ha	0.11	6.26	0.54	1.3	(Endalkachew et al., 2012)
	10 t/ha	0.13	7.25	0.58	1.5	
3	0 t/ha	0.27	6.17	0.53	1.35	(Misganaw et al., 2012)
	10 t/ha	0.31	7.84	0.56	1.64	
4	0 t/ha	0.15	7.1	0.07	1.69	(Ejue et al., 2020)
	30 t/ha	0.21	17.7	0.17	2.79	
5	0 t/ha	0.27	6.03	0.53	1.43	(Ambaw et al., 2012)
	10 t/ha	0.32	7.4	0.60	1.68	

Water Holding Capacity:

(Gavili et al., 2019) Biochar's water-retention properties make it a useful weapon in the fight against climate-related desertification. The enhancement of arid soils in sub-Saharan Africa is one of biochar's many practical applications. This region's soil quality is frequently subpar due to the high concentration of sedimentary material created by granite cleavage. Due to the persistent drought, the soils in this region have become desiccated and acidic (pH 4). (Gwenzi et al., 2015). The addition of 1.2% biochar enhances the porosity of silty loam from 50.9% to 52.2%. Adekiya et al. (2020) demonstrated that biochar may enhance water infiltration, thereby reducing soil loss. Soil loss was minimal at 30 t/ha biochar application rates (118 kg/ha in 2017 and 68.25 kg/ha in 2018), whereas it was greatest at control sites (355 kg/ha in 2017 and 365 kg/ha in 2018). The porosity of biochar is known to have a substantial effect on its water-holding capacity. Both large and tiny fissures influence the total porosity of the soil. According to Aggehu et al. (2017), the water content of the soil increased by 14.6% when biochar and fertilizer were administered together. This study demonstrates that increasing soil water capacity necessitates soil porosity improvement. The incorporation of 5.2% municipal green waste as biochar into residual sand increased its water retention capacity from 0.11 to 0.20 g/cm² (Mukherjee and Lal, 2013). (Ali et al., 2017) Plants experience salinity stress when soil moisture is significantly lost. Approximately 18% of the time, biochar increases WHC. According to Yu et al. (2014), biochar increases porosity and surface area, thereby improving water storage. Research indicates that biochar may enhance water retention regardless of the type of soil (Razzaghi et al., 2020).

Biochar's effects on soil structure:

Biochar has the potential to improve the physical properties of the soil, specifically its surface area, porosity, holding capacity, oxygen absorption, and water absorption. According to Janus et al. (2015) and Liu (2014), the soil's surface area and pore structure must increase for soil microbes and fungi to colonize and contribute to the soil's capacity to assimilate nutrients. It has been demonstrated (Zhang et al., 2013; Mukherjee et al., 2013) that an increase in soil porosity stimulates nitrification by increasing the soil's capacity to retain moisture and air. Soil with a higher porosity may assimilate nitrification inhibitors faster, thereby accelerating the nitrification process (Mukherjee et al., 2013). Numerous studies (such as those on phenolics) have proven this. However, it takes many months for nitrifiers to colonize charcoal (Bai et al., 2015). By altering the soil's composition, biochar enables nitrogen-fixing microbes to colonize the charcoal's fissures. Biochar utilization benefits both symbiotic and free-living microorganisms. The bulk density of sandy loamy soils decreases from 1.61 to 1.51g/cm³ when 2% peanut husk biochar is applied (Mukherjee and Lal, 2013). Biochar-supplemented soil has a lower bulk density, resulting in improved soil structure, aggregation, and aeration.

Table 4: Effect of biochar on soil physical properties

S.no	Rate of Biochar (t/ha)	Porosity %	Moisture Content %	Bulk Density Mg/m ³	References
1	0 t/ha	40.4	9.6 %	1.58	(Arun et al., 2020)
	30 t/ha	59.2	14.9 %	1.08	
2	0 t/ha	62.4	8.7 %	1.42	(Rahman et al., 2011)
	25 t/ha	73.5	12.8 %	1.01	
3	0 t/ha	50.4	10.5 %	1.30	(Hui et al., 2021)
	50 t/ha	61.7	18.3 %	0.85	
4	0 t/ha	50.9	11.9 %	0.99	(Chang et al., 2021)
	2 t/ha	52.8	14.6 %	0.91	
5	0 t/ha	40.0	10.1 %	1.59	(Timothy et al., 2020)
	30 t/ha	66.0	15.9 %	0.91	

Effects of biochar on soil enzymes and microbial diversity:

Biochar affects microbial diversity, growth, and soil enzymes. Both Ippito et al. (2016) and Huang et al. (2018) investigated the stimulating effects of biochar. According to research by Huang et al. (2018), increasing the concentration of biochar in soil from 1% to 5% decreased the quantity of soil microorganisms. Numerous researchers (Chen et al., 2013; Huang et al., 2018; others) have confirmed that the inclusion of biochar increased the number of 16S rRNA gene copies in the bacterial-dominated microbial community. 5% biochar reduced bacterial and fungal gene copies by 74% and 25%, respectively, compared to the control in both investigations. Bacterial and fungal proliferation was also found to be more favorable in neutral or slightly alkaline soil than in acidic soil (Jagdish et al., 2020). According to Diaz et

al. (2020), biochar application to a wheat crop increased catalase and urease activity. Wang et al. determined that in 2022, urease and catalase activity in soil treated with 3% biochar was greater than T0 without biochar (18.06% and 30.92%).

Biochar produced at both high and low pyrolysis temperatures results in substantially greater microbial diversity than the control plot (Singh et al., 2022). After 1%–2% biochar addition, soil pH was in the 7–7.5 range; after 5%–10% biochar application, soil pH increased to 8.5, further indicating that the soil is not a favourable environment for microbial growth and precludes the coding gene copies of bacteria and fungi. Biochar has been demonstrated to benefit both arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) and ectomycorrhizal soil fungi (Elzobair et al., 2016). According to Wang et al. (2016), biochar modifications do not always have a positive influence on microorganisms. If applied to a system, biochar may reduce the number and efficiency of denitrifying microorganisms. Denitrifying microorganisms may also reduce the availability of soil nitrogen and increase N₂O emissions. The addition of biochar increases soil N₂ because the number of denitrifying microorganisms decreases. So that plants can use them, soil microbes break down large organic compounds into smaller monomers. For this type of metabolism, bacteria produce extracellular enzymes such as glucosidase, laccase, invertase, galactosidase, laccase, cellulase, phosphatase, and those required for carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus recycling (Bell et al., 2014; Patil and Yadav, 2018). It was investigated how biochar affected the enzymes invertase, urease, and alkaline phosphatase. Huang et al. (2017) discovered that 2% biochar added to soil increased enzyme activity. Enzyme activity decreases as the concentration of biochar increases. Even at a modest concentration of biochar (2.5%; Jin et al., 2016; Bhaduri et al., 2016), alkaline phosphatase and alkaline phosphomonoesterase activities increased, indicating an increase in P cycling enzyme activity.

Biochar's use in the remediation of Soil HMs contamination:

Biochar can be produced by a variety of factors that influence its interaction with HMs. Biochar's high surface area, CEC, and oxygen-containing functional groups allow it to retain, stabilize, and inactivate toxic heavy metals, thereby reducing their biotoxicity and bioavailability in the soil environment (Ma et al., 2022).

Lead, chromium, mercury, copper, cadmium, and arsenic are, however, the most dangerous pollutants for HMs. Biochar has the ability to remove or resolve soil HMs through complexation, reduction, and cation exchange. HMs may be converted from inorganic to organic forms if this happens (Lahori et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2018).

Copper (Cu):

According to Meier et al. (2017), biochar made from poultry manure has a high affinity for copper due to its high OH content and negative zeta potential. Liming increases the soil's acidity, thereby immobilizing Cu. This enhances the interaction between the copper ion and other functional groups, such as phenolic-OH and C=O, on the surface of biochar. Biochar ashes derived from wood shavings (Rechberger et al., 2017) or bamboo (Zhang et al., 2018) are efficient sources of hydroxides and carbonates that facilitate the formation of CuCO₃ and Cu(OH)₂, the most important Cu (II) adsorbents. Biochar's alkalinity must be used to increase soil pH in order to facilitate copper immobilization (Gonzaga et al., 2018). As stated previously, dissolved organic carbon in the soil has a significant effect on copper mobility (Cheng et al., 2020). It has been demonstrated that incorporating biochar made from chicken manure into copper-polluted soil accelerates the decomposition of soil organic carbon and converts Cu(II) into more soluble copper ion complexes (Park et al., 2011).

Arsenic (As):

Arsenic and phosphorus share comparable chemical properties; the presence of the latter in the soil has a substantial effect on the mobility of the former (Ahmad et al., 2016). An extremely positive correlation exists between phosphate and arsenate concentrations in arsenic-exposed soils. After soils were treated with biochar containing phosphorus derived from pine needles, rice straw, and soybean, competition between soluble phosphate Arsenate accumulates on the adsorption sites of soil particles, facilitating the release of arsenic from the solid phase of the soil and elevating its concentration in the pore water(Ahmad et al., 2014).

Cadmium (Cd):

According to Gao et al. (2019), the soil pH significantly influences the Cd activity in soils. Researchers have demonstrated that the alkaline components of biochar can bond with and absorb Cd in soils. Carbonate (CO₃²⁻), phosphate (PO₄³⁻), and OH⁻ ions comprise these constituents. In soils, the free Cd(II) precipitates as Cd₃(PO₄)₂, CdCO₃, and Cd(OH)₂. Strong adsorption affinity is the primary factor reducing Cd bioavailability; this factor is influenced by the abundance of functional groups and higher specific surface area of biochar, which promote Cd immobilization (Qian et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019).

Lead (Pb):

The interaction between cation donors and electron acceptors in soybean biochar enhances Pb immobilization. Basic elements (CO₃²⁻, OH⁻, and other alkaline earth elements Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) in biochar may interact with Pb(II) via cation exchange and precipitation, resulting in substantial Pb immobilization. Phosphate ions, which are abundant in biochar derived from poultry manure and municipal sediment, may react with lead (II) to produce insoluble compounds such as Pb₅(PO₄)₃Cl, Pb₅(PO₄)₃OH, and -Pb₉(PO₄)₆ (Ahmad et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2018), thereby reducing lead mobility. By forming strong covalent bonds with N-containing functional groups (particularly NH₂) on its surface, biochar made from vegetable waste has been shown to reduce the concentration of NH₄OAc-extracted Pb (Igalavithana et al., 2019).

Mercury (Hg):

Mercury is one of the most hazardous heavy metals found in contaminated environments. Biochar decreases mercury toxicity in soil because it is an effective soil remediation technique (Cheng et al., 2020). Wang et al. (2019) found that thiol groups and sulfoxide groups in biochar made from hardwoods can react with Hg(II) ions to make -S(Hg)- and [Hg(OSR₂)₆]²⁺, respectively. The carboxyl group in biochar and the Hg(II) ion in soil endure a coordination reaction, resulting in the precipitation of a complex of -COOHg⁺. In addition, Xing et al. (2019) discovered that rice husk biochar stimulates the synthesis of sulfides and mercury-sulfur coordination compounds more effectively than wheat straw biochar. This is because rice fiber biochar contains more sulfate. Methylmercury (MeHg) is a highly toxic and bioaccumulative form of mercury that forms in soils when Hg combines with methylamine (Zhang et al., 2010). Methylation is a unique environmental biogeochemical process. The

discharge of rice root exudates increases soil pH and inhibits methylation effectively, whereas the use of alkaline biochar decreases soil pH and increases Hg methylation.

Chromium (Cr):

The soil contains both Cr (VI) and Cr (III) forms of chromium. Therefore, Cr immobilization in soils requires a complex combination of adsorption, reduction, and precipitation processes. The primary manifestations of the mechanism governing the interaction between Cr and biochar are the surface adsorption of Cr (VI) by oxygen-containing functional groups in biochar (such as C-O, C=O, -COOH, and -OH) and the reduction process involving the electrons that biochar provides (Lyu et al., 2017). By participating in adsorption-reduction activities and contributing to the formation of Cr₂O₃ and/or Cr(OH)₃ precipitation, biochar specifically converts Cr(VI) into Cr(III), which is less toxic and more soluble (Xia et al., 2019). Choppala et al. (2016) utilized biochar made from chicken manure to supplement Cr combined, organic matter-deficient soil. As a consequence, soil respiration and microbial activity increased, and the soil's nutrient and organic carbon content increased significantly. Due to the interaction between these factors, microbial Cr (VI) reduction had a greater impact, and Cr biotoxicity was reduced. Mandal et al. (2017) found that biochar made from animal manure reduced Cr (VI) in acidic soil more effectively than in alkaline soil.

Conclusion:

Biochar has the potential to be used in the future to address the issue of soil fertility deficiency in numerous regions around the world. Biochar increases the soil's ability to retain water, which is essential for the development of thriving vegetation in arid regions. In addition, biochar may reduce the need for artificial fertilizers by absorbing and retaining nutrients, then gradually releasing them and making them available to plants when combined with compost. Future agricultural industries may generate and distribute these manufactured products to farmers. Biochar's adsorbent properties could be a game-changer for water purification systems. In addition to absorbing microorganisms, biochar eliminates both dissolved and suspended particles. Biochar filters may be more cost-effective and efficient than carbon filters. Its selective adsorption properties have the potential to be very beneficial to the dye industry. Biochar's capacity to absorb or store carbon, for instance, increases its potential for mitigating climate change. In the pharmaceutical industry, it can be used to effectively eliminate contaminants. It has the potential to become a vital resource for numerous emerging industries, such as the food and beverage industry, fertilizer production, agriculture, and the pharmaceutical industry. Utilizing biochar in soils has the potential to significantly improve soil fertility and stimulate plant growth. Due to the versatility of biochar feedstocks, which include a broad variety of biomass sources and can be pyrolyzed at a range of temperatures, various types of biochar are utilized to remediate different types of soil. Biochar possesses an abundance of healthy components, a high number of exchangeable cations, and a vast surface area. These attributes may contribute to improved soil quality following biochar treatment. Due to the material's expansive surface area and intricate capillary structure, it has a greater capacity to retain water and can support a greater variety of microorganisms. There may be a relationship between the quantity of cations that can be exchanged, the capacity to do so, and the quantity of nutrients present. The high liming content of biochar is a solution to the problem of overly acidic soils. Therefore, enhancements in soil physical, chemical, and biological properties increase plant yield by increasing the quantity of nutrients, enhancing their availability, reducing nutrient leaching, and controlling gaseous nutrient losses. Biochar application to HM-contaminated soil is a

feasible, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective method. The multitude of thermochemical conversion processes used to produce biochar, as well as the feedstock materials employed, the pyrolysis temperature, and the residence time, have all had substantial impacts on its performance properties.

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